

Data Management Plan for Systematic Review Protocol: Comparing Supervised Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms for Movement Intention Recognition in Individuals with Upper-Limb Amputation

Edgar Francisco Arcos Hurtado
Universidad Santiago de Cali

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Data Management Plan

This Data Management Plan is a complementary document to the full protocol of the systematic review, which has been officially registered in **PROSPERO** under the identifier **CRD420251133179**, and is also archived in **Zenodo** with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.16937811. The purpose of this plan is to provide detailed guidance on data extraction, storage, appraisal, synthesis, and sharing, ensuring transparency, and reproducibility.

1. Data Extraction

Two reviewers will independently extract data from each included study using a standardized data extraction form. Extracted variables will include:

- Study identification: DOI, authors, year of publication, country.
- Study design: experimental, comparative, or validation study.
- Population: sample size, demographics, inclusion/exclusion criteria, amputation characteristics.
- Intervention: type of algorithm (CNN, LSTM, MLP, etc.), datasets used, training methods, feature extraction techniques.
- Comparator: supervised algorithms (SVM, KNN, Random Forest, etc.).

- Outcomes: accuracy, F1-score, latency, error rate, training/inference time, real-time performance.
- Quality assessment indicators: completeness of reporting, reproducibility, dataset description, risk of bias elements.

Discrepancies between reviewers will be resolved by discussion or by consulting a third reviewer.

2. Data Storage and Organization

Data will be stored in encrypted Excel/CSV files and managed through collaborative platforms (Google Sheets or Rayyan). Backups will be maintained in secure institutional servers. Each entry will be uniquely identified to ensure traceability between publications and extracted data. Version control will be applied to track changes in the dataset.

Bibliographic references will be managed using **Mendeley** to ensure accurate citation, deduplication of records, and structured organization of references.

3. Study Selection Process

The selection of studies will follow the **PRISMA 2020** guidelines. Titles and abstracts will be screened independently by two reviewers, followed by full-text assessment of potentially eligible articles. A PRISMA flow diagram will be used to document the identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion phases. Disagreements will be resolved by consensus or by consulting a third reviewer.

4. Critical Appraisal and Risk of Bias Assessment

Risk of bias will be assessed using tailored checklists adapted from AMSTAR-2 guidelines. Specific criteria will include study design quality, transparency in methods, dataset availability, reproducibility of algorithms, and completeness of performance reporting. At least two reviewers will independently assess risk of bias, with consensus procedures in place for discrepancies. Results of appraisal will be summarized in tabular format and included in the review synthesis.

5. Data Synthesis

Quantitative outcomes will be combined through meta-analysis if sufficient homogeneity exists across datasets and performance metrics, applying random-effects models to account for methodological variability. Where meta-analysis is not feasible, narrative synthesis will be

performed. Additionally, qualitative evidence (e.g., methodological descriptions, contextual factors) will be analyzed using thematic coding approaches, following stages of familiarization, and open and axial coding

6. Coding and Thematic Analysis

Thematic coding will be applied to extract meaningful concepts from study descriptions. This will involve:

- Open coding: identification of key concepts and methodological practices.
- Axial coding: grouping of codes into broader categories (e.g., algorithm families, dataset characteristics, performance measures).
- Selective coding: synthesis of central themes related to algorithm performance and applicability in prosthetic control.

This process ensures transparency and consistency in qualitative synthesis, while allowing the identification of gaps and emerging patterns.

7. Quality Assurance

To ensure reliability and reproducibility:

- Data will be extracted and coded by at least two reviewers independently.
- Coding guidelines will be documented and iteratively refined.
- Triangulation of data sources will be used where possible.
- Reflexivity and peer debriefing will be encouraged to minimize researcher bias.

8. Data Availability and Sharing

Upon completion of the review, the full dataset (extraction tables, coding frameworks, risk of bias assessments) will be deposited in an open-access repository (e.g., Zenodo or OSF). A DOI will be assigned to enable citation and reuse, ensuring transparency and adherence to FAIR principles.

References

Arcos Hurtado, Edgar Francisco. (2025). *Systematic Review Protocol: Comparing Supervised Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms for Movement Intention Recognition in Individuals with Upper-Limb Amputation*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16937812>